

Fig.2 Example of topics generated by GoLEM

Fig.3 The same group of topics represented chronologically

A strong emphasis is put on the visualisation of results in GoLEM, e.g. as graphs, time series, maps or scatter plots, which allow to take into account local circumstances and to trace the impact of historical and spatial factors on the dynamics of literary processes. GoLEM also allows for determining and visualising relationships between named entities in the corpus. Fig.4 shows the Gephi-made visualisation of co-appearance relationships of persons in the corpus.

Fig.4 Clustered visualisation of persons from the literary-studies anthologies

GoLEM stands out from other web-based text analysis tools thanks to its close relation between uploaded texts and their metadata: users can add metadata to documents in bulk, filter texts by metadata and group texts based on metadata or keyword searches to perform comparative analyses of subcorpora. Moreover, GoLEM takes into account different levels of user experience, from basic to expert. The system also allows user intervention and iterative adaptation of individual sub-processes of the processing pipeline.

Acknowledgements

This work was conducted in the project *DARIAH-PL: digital research infrastructure for arts & humanities*, Polish Smart

Growth Operational Programme 2014-2020 #POIR.04.02.00-00-D006/20.

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